

Oligo (Simultaneous Multielement) Analysis of Calcite Ore Sample : A Voltammetric Approach

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Calcite is a known source of calcium, in which calcium constitutes the major part. It is associated with some other elements, such as Al, Mg, Fe, Na, K, Ti, Mn and Cu, which are present in trace amounts¹. Recently DCP, DPP and related techniques have been successfully used for simultaneous determination of metals in natural origin samples². The methods are highly sensitive and accurate. The results of voltammetric analysis on calcite ore sample have been discussed in the present communication.

Results and Discussion

In KCl, the DC and DP polarograms of the sample solutions showed three well-defined polarographic waves/peaks with $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values equal to $-0.06/-0.08$, $-0.86/-0.84$, $-1.20/-1.14$, $-1.54/-1.62$ V vs SCE, indicating the presence of Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} (Figs. 1a, 2a).

Fig 1 Direct current polarogram of calcite sample (100 mg/100 ml) in (a) 0.2 M KCl + 0.001 % gelatin, pH 4.00 ± 0.02 , (b) 0.1 M HCl, pH 0.0 ± 0.02 , (c) and (d) 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium chloride at pH 2.00 and 8.00 ± 0.02 respectively, and (e) 0.1 M sodium acetate, pH 4.7 ± 0.02

In HCl, the DC and DP polarograms of the sample solution showed a wave/peak with $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values equal to

$-0.78\text{V}/-0.82\text{V}$ vs SCE indicating the presence of Ti^{IV} , besides Cu, Co and Fe (Figs. 1b, 2b).

Fig 2 Differential pulse polarogram of calcite sample (100 mg/100 ml) in (a) 0.2 M KCl + 0.001 % gelatin, pH 4.00 ± 0.02 , (b) 1 M HCl, pH 0.0 ± 0.02 , (c) and (d) 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium chloride at pH 2.00 and 8.00 ± 0.02 respectively, and (e) 0.1 M sodium acetate pH 4.7 ± 0.02

In tetrabutylammonium chloride, the DC and DP polarograms of the sample solution showed two distinct waves/peaks at pH 2.00 ± 0.02 with $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values equal to $-2.08/-2.08$ and $-2.36/-2.26$ due to Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} , whereas two other peaks/waves were observed at pH 8.00 ± 0.02 with $E_{1/2}/E_p$ equal to $-1.94/-1.98$ and $-2.20\text{V}/-2.20\text{V}$ due to the presence of Na^{I} and K^{I} (Figs. 1c, 2c).

In sodium acetate, the DC and DP polarograms of the sample solution showed single peak/wave with $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values equal to $-0.53\text{V}/-0.50\text{V}$ corresponding to Al^{III} (Figs. 1d, 2d).

Quantitative analysis of the sample by DCP and DPP. To confirm the presence of the said metal ions in the sample, a definite quantity of the standard solution of each metal ion was added to the analyte and polarograms were recorded under the aforesaid experimental conditions. An

NOTE

TABLE I—RESULTS OF CALCITE ORE SAMPLE (mg/100 ml) ANALYSIS FOR ITS METALS CONTENT

Metal ion	Parameter	DCP Mode		DPP Mode	
		Added	Found*	Added	Found*
Cu ^{II}	Amount	— 0.127	0.105 0.231	— 0.127	0.105 0.232
	Recovery(%)		99.5		100.0
	SD		0.02		0.01
Fe ^{II}	Amount	— 0.335	0.335 0.667	— 0.335	0.335 0.667
	Recovery(%)		99.5		99.5
	SD		0.07		0.06
Fe ^{III}	Amount	— 0.335	0.363 0.695	— 0.335	0.363 0.698
	Recovery(%)		99.5		100.0
	SD		0.06		0.06
Mn ^{II}	Amount	— 0.027	0.031 0.058	— 0.027	0.031 0.058
	Recovery(%)		100.0		100.0
	SD		0.04		0.03
Ti ^{IV}	Amount	— 0.089	0.089 0.177	— 0.089	0.089 0.177
	Recovery(%)		99.4		99.4
	SD		0.05		0.05
Ca ^{II}	Amount	— 40.07	41.500 80.990	— 40.070	41.500 81.000
	Recovery(%)		99.2		99.4
	SD		0.01		0.05
Mg ^{II}	Amount	— 0.500	0.500 0.995	— 0.500	0.500 0.998
	Recovery(%)		99.5		99.8
	SD		0.02		0.02
Na ^I	Amount	— 0.595	0.604 1.192	— 0.595	0.604 1.195
	Recovery(%)		99.4		99.6
	SD		0.02		0.02
K ^I	Amount	— 0.586	0.585 1.165	— 0.586	0.585 1.165
	Recovery(%)		99.4		99.4
	SD		0.02		0.02
Al ^{III}	Amount	— 1.061	1.790 2.839	— 1.061	1.790 2.843
	Recovery(%)		99.5		99.7
	SD		0.03		0.03

*Results are average of four determinations

increase in the wave/peak height of each metal ion signal was observed without any change in $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values.

Based on the presence of these metal ions in the sample, some synthetic samples of varying concentration of the ions were prepared and their polarograms were recorded in the identical experimental conditions, as discussed earlier. No change in $E_{1/2}/E_p$ values of the aforesaid metal ions was observed. The proportionality of the concentration of each metal ion to its wave/peak height was also observed. This reconfirms the possibility of an accurate oligo qualitative as well as quantitative determina-

tion of the metal ions in the sample using DCP/DPP methods.

The precision and percentage recovery of the spiked sample for the determination of the metal ions are reported in Table 1. The results indicate that the percentage recovery is over 99% for all the metal ions. Table 2 shows the final analysis results. The results were compared with those obtained using AAS method, which are in excellent agreement. However, the proposed voltammetric procedure is found to be highly useful for the determination of species in different oxidation states in the sample, e.g. Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}

in the present case, which is otherwise not possible using AAS method⁴. The comparative and statistical data reveal the superiority of the voltammetric method for such an analysis.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF AAS AND VOLTAMMETRIC TRACE ANALYSIS DATA FOR CALCITE ORE SAMPLES

Metal ion	Amount found (mg g ⁻¹)	
	AAS	Voltammetry
Cu ^{II}	1.05	1.05
Fe ^{II}		3.35
Fe ^{III}	7.70	3.63
Mn ^{II}	0.30	0.31
Ti ^{IV}	0.80	0.89
Ca ^{II}	406.60	415.00
Mg ^{II}	44.90	50.00
Na ^I	6.00	6.04
K ^I	5.80	5.85
Al ^{III}	17.50	17.90

Experimental

Calcite ore samples were collected from Rumpura area located at a distance of about 5 km south of Sesai village, in Sagar District, M.P. A 1 km² area of the Rumpura deposit was selected for sampling and 25 such samples from different depths were collected.

Polarographic measurements were made on an Elico CL-90 polarograph. The electrode system consisted of a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as working electrode, a coiled platinum wire as auxiliary electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. The electrochemical cell used had the provision for inserting a bubbler for deaerating the solution using purified nitrogen gas. pH measurements were made on a Systronics 335 pH meter.

All chemicals were used of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions of KCl (2M), HCl (1M), tetrabutylammonium chloride, sodium acetate (0.1M) were used. Solutions (0.01M) of Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Na^I, K^I

and Al^{III} were prepared in double-distilled water. Gelatin solution (0.01%) was prepared in hot distilled water.

Finely pulverised calcite sample (1.0 g) was dissolved in 1M HCl (10 ml) and the final volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water¹.

To search out for the presence of the various metal ions in the sample, different supporting electrolytes were used⁵. (i) Potassium chloride : To calcite sample solution (10 ml), were added 2M KCl and 0.01% gelatin maximum suppressor (10 ml each) and the final volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 4.00 ± 0.02. (ii) Hydrochloric acid : To calcite sample solution (10 ml), 1M HCl (10 ml) was added and the final volume made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 0.0 ± 0.02. (iii) Tetrabutylammonium chloride : To the sample solution (10 ml), 1M tetrabutylammonium chloride (10 ml) was added and the final volume made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The analysis of the sample was carried out at two pH values, 2.00 ± 0.02 and 8.00 ± 0.002. (iv) Sodium acetate : The sample solutions (10 ml) was mixed with 1M sodium acetate (10 ml) and the final volume made upto 100 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.7 ± 0.02. Each analyte was taken in a polarographic cell, pure nitrogen gas was bubbled through the solutions for 15 min and then the polarograms were recorded.

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